

Educational Status of Differently Abled Persons and Developed Policies in India

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ABSTRACT

A powerful instrument of social change is Education and often initiates upward movement in the social structure. Most important vehicle for Children with Disabilities (CWDs) is Education. A considerable segment of CWDs excluded from educational system in India. According to 2011 Census in India, the percentage of disabled persons who are Illiterate is about 45.48. The disabled male percentage with Illiteracy is about 37.63 and for disabled females is about 55.44 that means disabled females are more Illiterate than disabled males. The percentage of disabled persons who are Literate is about 54.52. The disabled persons who are Literate but below Primary level is about 10.59%, have primary level of education but below Middle is about 13.26%, have middle but below Matric / Secondary is about 9.13%, have Secondary level of Education but below Graduate is about 12.86, have graduate and above is about 4.65%. However, Indian Government stated to take some important steps for CWDs. Various report, commission, policy, committee and programme is responsible to improve the educational status of special persons. Such report, commission, policy, committee and programme are Sergeant report, Kothari commission, National Education Policy, National Policy on Education and Programme of Action, Integrated Education for the Disabled Children, Bahuril Islam Committee, Programme of Action, District Primary Education Programme, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan. The objective of maximum of this is to take disabled children into general education system and to improve the quality of education.

Keywords: Differently Abled Persons, Children with Disabilities Educational Status, Inclusive Education, Developed Policies

INTRODUCTION

Disability is an umbrella term that covering impairments, activity limitations and participation restrictions. In another way, it is defined as a physical and mental condition that limits a person's movements, senses, and activities. As per Census 2011 in India, out of 121 Cr population, about 2.68 Cr persons are Physically and Mentally Challenged that means 2.21% of total population (Majumder C, 2019). Among this special grouped population, 56% (1.5 Cr) are males and 44% (1.18 Cr) are females. Mostly, disabled persons are founds in low and middle income countries. Worldwide, in primary education, approximately one hundred and thirteen million children are not enrolled (Department of International Development, 2001). In India, more often Physically Challenged Persons are denied from education. An estimation suggests that in India, twenty five million children are out of school (MHRD, 2003 statistics, cited in World Bank, 2004).

One of the socially created phenomenon is basically Disability. The fact is that many children and adults suffered from disabilities excluded from mainstream education benefits. Disabled persons are segregated from education system because of social negligence and absence of support system in the home and inadequacy of sufficient facilities in

schools particularly. However, education is the most important medium for social, economic and political transformation. Socialization of children with disabilities (CWD) through education receives an unremarkably important roles in societies such as India where social exclusion of Physically Challenged Persons (PCPs) is significant. Indisputably, the literacy level of Physically Challenged Persons (PCPs) is very low in India. Very poor educational outcomes for children with disabilities remain in developing countries specially. Most of disabled persons do not get the full benefits of education. However, some policies in India has started to display some concern for Physically Challenged students. Education is utmost significant to lift up the socio-economic status of PCPs. But education of disabled persons has not received adequate intentness and resources that it requires. Physically Challenged Persons (PCPs), few who are enrolled in schools are not given equal opportunity for middle secondary and higher education levels. Many Disabled persons are educated but they do not get any work for earning in our society.

However, in India the existing situation began to change. Indian policies has started to understand as for all people that education is essential for children and adults with

disabilities in itself and helpful for participating in employment and other sites of social activity. The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) has initiated various programmes to give educational opportunities to PCPs in an environment that is inclusive (Ghoshal S.K., 2018). Government of India also understands the needs of appropriate vocational training skills to make them self faithful and productive members of society. But, the scheme coverage has stayed limited. Non Governmental Organizations (NGOs) has a biggest role to improve the life of disabled persons in our society.

Educational Status of Disabled Persons in India

India is the world’s largest democracy. India has a countless challenges for ensuring access to education for over all 200 million (20 Cr) children aged 6 to 13 years. As per 2011 National Census, 1.05% of school going children have a problem like disability (2.13 million = 21 Lakhs 30 Thousand); of these 28% (5 Lakhs 88 Thousand) are not accessing school. Particularly 44% of disabled children are not accessing school have complex and multiple forms of activity limitations and functioning difficulties (Bakhshi et al, 2017).

Education is an fruitful tool for socio-economic empowerment which can develop the career of specially disabled ones. However, in all over the world, many children and adults with disabilities have been eliminated from mainstream education benefits. Thus, it is required to promote inclusive education for special children. Inclusive education is very attractive decision for disabled children. From the data on education of disabled persons, it is cleared that special children have far poorer educational benefits with compared to non-disabled peers. As per 2004 World Health Survey disability respondents had significantly lower rates of primary school completion. In lower income countries, the condition is more vulnerable. On disability, two important sources in India are Census and NSSO (National Sample Survey Office). Both sources express depressing and gloomy picture of educational status of special population as compared to the general population trends. Even among disabled group, handsome proportions were educated only up to primary or middle level both in urban and rural areas. Higher education for this type of peoples is very challenging. The situation is more hard for girls children with disability. Higher education for primary and middle school level disabled individuals in rural and urban areas is insignificant in India like country. However, in NSSO (National Sample Survey Organization) data some improvement is shown.

Worldwide Education Outcomes for Non Disabled and Disabled Respondents at Primary School level

Individuals		Low Income Countries		High Income Countries		All Countries	
		Not Disabled (%)	Disabled (%)	Not Disabled (%)	Disabled (%)	Not Disabled (%)	Disabled (%)
Completion of Primary School	Male	55.6	45.6*	72.3	61.7*	61.3	50.6*
	Female	42.0	32.9*	72.0	59.3*	52.9	41.7*
	18-49 years old	60.3	47.8*	83.1	69.0*	67.4	53.2*
	50-59 years old	44.3	30.8*	68.1	52.0*	52.7	37.6*
	60 and Above	30.7	21.2*	53.6	46.5*	40.6	32.3*

Source: World Health Survey, Geneva, World Health Organization, 2002-2004

Distribution of Percentage of Educational Status of Disabled Persons by Sector in India

Educational status	1991		2002	
	Rural (%)	Urban (%)	Rural (%)	Urban (%)
Illiterate	70.1	46.2	59.0	40.0
Primary	20.3	29.8	24.4	28.8
Middle	5.3	11.0	9.7	13.7
Secondary	2.3	6.4	3.8	7.8
Higher Secondary	0.8	2.8	2.1	5.1
Graduation and Above	0.4	3.1	1.0	4.6
Not Reported	0.8	0.8	0.1	0.1
Received Vocational Training	1.2	3.1	1.5	3.6
Engineering	20.2	26.6	20	25
Non-Engineering	79.8	73.4	80	75
ALL	12652000	3502000	14085000	4406000

Source: NSSO Rounds 47th and 58th, 1991, 2002

Distribution of Percentage of Educational Level of Disabled Persons by gender in India

Level of Education	India		
	Persons (%)	Males (%)	Females (%)
Illiterate	45.48	37.63	55.44
Literate	54.52	62.37	44.56
Literate but below Primary	10.59	11.38	9.58
Primary but below Middle	13.26	14.65	11.49
Middle but below Matric / Secondary	9.13	10.79	7.03
Matric / Secondary but below Graduate	12.86	15.54	9.45
Graduate and Above	4.65	5.60	3.44

Source: Census, 2011, India

Percentage of Disabled Children in India

Age Groups (Years)	Disabled Children (%)
0-4	1.14
5-6	1.54
10-19	1.82

Source: Census, 2011, India

Policy for Physically Challenged Person's (PCPs)- From Special Education to Inclusive Education

In the general education classroom, the inclusion of students with special needs is the major topic of discussion for many years. Inclusion education means that all of the students are part of the school association, regardless of their weaknesses and strengths (Walsh M, 2018). These kind of students deserve to get full access to all resources and social interactions that are stayed in the general education classroom. The ultimate aim of many schools is to create a classroom that has the few restrictive environment to meet the needs of all learners or students, including disabled students also. In present time, the education of Physically Challenged Persons (PCPs) is converted from segregation to integration, and now to inclusion. In India, the educational system aids elimination of disabled children from the education system, even methodology of teaching is not favorable for them. Due to not friendly communication and not welcoming approach of many schools, disabled children are not wished to go to school regularly. Even the school staff is not trained to give essential educational and communication training to the disabled children.

In the India, the different types of commission, committees, acts and schemes is implemented and constituted for Physically Challenged Persons (PCPs) for their education, by cooperation with Governmental and Non Governmental Organization (NGO). Government also aids in learning through multiplicative and alternative modes for PCPs. The National Institute for the Hearing Handicapped (NIHH) gave several informal and formal talks to students, faculty and administration about the importance of 'sign language' in deaf education and rehabilitation (Zeshan et al). Indian Sign Language Cell is run by NIHH which help in the development of teaching material to teach Indian Sign Language (ISL), training of ISL interpreters, to train deaf persons to become teacher of sign language. NIHH also help in sign language training for hearing stuff at educational institution, for parents and family members of hearing handicapped. In the different places of country and their variations, documentation of sign language vocabulary is used.

Policies associated to Education for Children with Disabilities in India

Education for CWDs is important. A considerable segment of CWDs excluded from educational system in India. Nevertheless, India Government started to take some important steps for CWDs. The various policies associated to education for CWDs in Indian context is summarized below-

Policy	Objective
Sergeant report/ The Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE), 1944	The Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE) published a comprehensive report called the Sergeant Report in 1944 (National Council of Educational Research And Training, 2006). According to this report, handicapped children were to be sent to special schools only when the nature and extent of their defects made this necessary. This report was the very important report to make policy on 'Integration' of disabled children in general schools in India.
The National Education Commission/ Kothari Commission (1964-1966)	The Kothari Commission is the first education commission of independent India, observed that, for the handicapped children, education should be an inseparable part of the education system. The Objective of Kothari commission is to integrate the handicapped children and general children in the same education system. The commission recommended experimentation with programmes that is integrated in order to bring as many children as possible into this programmes (Alur M, 2002).
National Education Policy (NEP), 1968	The objectives of this education policy is to expand of educational facilities for mentally and physically handicapped children and to develop the 'Integrated Programme' that enabling handicapped children to study in regular schools.
National Policy on Education (NPE), 1986 and Programme of Action, 1992	The objective of this policy and programme is to integrate the physically and mentally impaired children with mainstream educational institutions.
Bahrul Islam Committee, 1988	The committee expressed that the state should wish to give free and universal elementary education to children with physical and mental disabilities. The state shall also give assistance to them for education and training at the secondary and higher levels. It also strongly emphasized on the promotion of integrated education and continuation of residential education.
Programme of Action , 1990, Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD)	Concentrated on the service training programmes for teachers, orientation programmes for administrators, development of supervisory expertise in the resource institution for school education at the block and district levels, and arrangement of incentives like supply of helps, appliances, textbooks and school uniforms.

Integrated Education for the Disabled Children (Revised 1987, 1989 and 1992)	This plan provided the funding for rehabilitation aids and equipment, educational material, resource teacher training, establishment of parent and preschool counseling centers, transport allowance, removal of architectural barriers in school buildings, etc.
Project Integrated Education for the Disabled (PIED), 1987	The National Council for Educational Research and Training (NCERT) implemented PIED with the financial support from UNICEF (The United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund), which provided support for the instructional material development, personnel training, put together community support, training of parents and coordinator of the project in rural and remote areas and difficult places. It also give support for identification and assessment of children with disabilities, resource room establishment, provision of helps and appliances and allowances for disabled children.
District Primary Education Programme, (DPEP), 1994	DPEP is the Centrally-Sponsored Scheme was launched on 1994. The main objective of DPEP is to promote inclusive education of children with disabilities in primary education level. It strongly emphasized to put local communities in change of education in their own area and enhance investment in primary education for inclusive education either in the formal system or through non formal education programme.
The National Action Plan for Inclusive in Education Of Children and Youth with Disabilities (IECYD), developed by the MHRD, 2005	Emphasizes on the children inclusion and young PwDs in all general educational settings from Early Childhood to Higher Education.
Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) (Education for All Campaign)	SSA is an Indian Government Programme. The objective of SSA is to universalize the elementary education between the age of 6 to 14 years. SSA gives financial support for inclusive education of children with special needs, besides other component.

Secondary Education Programmes and Scheme in India

In the field of education, the highest advisory body is Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE). The committee works on the Universalization of Secondary Education. The CABE Committee reports on the 'Common School System and Girls Education' and this committee has recommended that the curriculum should need flexible and appropriate to make up the diversity of school children, including those with disability in both non-cognitive and cognitive areas. The different types of schemes and programs associated to education for differently abled people in India context is summarized below-

Scheme	Objective	Coverage
Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan (RMSA), 2009-2010	Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan is a centrally sponsored scheme of the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), Government of India, for the development of secondary education in public schools throughout India. It was launched in March 2009. The principal objectives are to promote quality of secondary education and increase the total enrollment rate. It aims to give universal education for all children between 15-16 years of age.	Secondary schools of Government through the country.
Inclusive Education for the Disabled at Secondary Stage	The main objective is to enable disabled students to continue their education in an inclusive environment in regular schools at the secondary stage.	Covers disabled children in the secondary stage from classes IX to XII.

Policies associated to Higher Education for Physically Challenged Persons in India -

In India, the outcome of higher education for Physically Challenged Persons (PCPs) is unsatisfactory. However, University Grant Commission (UGC) has provided instruction to all colleges and universities for giving 3% reservation in admission for Physically Challenged Students, reservation of 3% for the PCPs in the Lecturer appointment. The different schemes and programs associated to higher education for disabled people in Indian context summarized below -

Scheme and Programme	Objective
Higher Education for Persons with Special Needs (HEPSN)	The University Grant Commission (UGC) has implemented a scheme called "Higher education for Persons with Special needs" (HEPSN) which is generally meant for creating an environment at the higher education institutions to enrich higher education learning experiences for disabled persons. Creating awareness about the capabilities of differently-abled persons, constructions aimed at improving accessibility, purchase of equipments to enrich learning etc. are the broad categories of assistance under this scheme.
Financial Assistance to Visually-Challenged Teachers (FAVCT)	This Scheme has been formulated to help visually challenged permanent teachers to pursue teaching and research with the help of a reader and by using teaching and learning aids by way of giving Reader's Allowance and funds for purchase of Braille books, recorded materials etc.

Upgradation of existing Polytechnics to integrate physically challenged persons	The Scheme has been created with the aim to integrate Persons with Disabilities (PWDs) for maintaining vocational and technical education.
Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU)	<i>Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU) provides several certificate and diploma courses for PwDs.</i>
Establishment of Equal Opportunity Cells in Universities	<i>Commission has financed Institution for establishing Equal Opportunity Cells who are responsible to observe the effective implementation of policies and programmes for disadvantaged group and the Cells give guidance and counselling in academic, financial, social and other matters.</i>
National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology	The National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been deemed as a Centrally Sponsored Scheme to leverage the potential of ICT, in teaching and learning process for the benefit of all the learners in Higher Education Institutions in any time any where way. This is hoped to be a major intervention in enhancing the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in Higher Education. It is also helpful for visually impaired students.

Scholarships for Physically Challenged Persons in India-

In India, the policy associated to education for Physically Challenged Persons (PCPs) is satisfactory compare to other areas. Government of India started various types of scholarships for PCP to boost up their self confidence. The various scholarships associated to education for disabled people in Indian context summarized below –

Scholarships	Objective
National Means-cum-Merit Scholarship (NMMS), 2008	Under this scheme, it is proposed to award 100,000 scholarships to the gifted or talented students whose parental income is not more than Rs 1,50,000/- per annum from all sources. This scholarships will be paid from class IX till class XII for a maximum period of four years.
Kendriya Vidyalaya Sangathan/ Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti	The human resource development ministry has decided to exempt disabled students from tuition fees at Kendriya Vidyalayas across India. Navodaya Vidyalaya Samiti was registered as a Society with the primary objective to give good quality modern education to the talented children predominantly from the rural areas, without regard to their family's socio-economic condition.
National Scholarships for PwDs	This scholarship are awarded for completing studies from class IX standard onwards with the students of cerebral palsy, mental retardation, multiple disabilities and people with profound or severe hearing impairment. This scholarship is given also to the students who are studying in Graduation and Post Graduation level courses, diploma and certificate level professional courses. Financial aids under this scheme is also provided for computer with editing software for blind/ deaf graduate and postgraduate students pursuing professional courses and give support to access software for cerebral palsy students.
Gayn Prabha Scholarship Scheme (Educational Support)	Under this Scheme, financial aid is provided to the disabled to gain Graduation, Post Graduation, Vocational training / Professional courses that leading to skill development and employment for the persons with disabilities (PwDs). It is very sad to say that this scheme is discontinued from 24 January, 2018.
Scholarship and other schemes of State Governments for Higher Education	State government run scholarships to PwDs for Graduation, Post Graduation, Engineering and Professional courses per month. Besides this Hostel allowance is offered.

Summary and Conclusion

According to 2011 Census in India, the percentage of disabled persons who are illiterate is about 45.48. The disabled males percentage with illiteracy is about 37.63 and in case of disabled females, the percentage of illiteracy is about 55.44 that means disabled females are more prone to illiteracy than disabled males. Overall, the educational outcomes for adults and children with disabilities remain poor throughout the world. No exception is found even in India also. Maximum number of Physically Challenged Persons (PCPs) are not provided equal opportunities for education and few disabled persons who are enrolled in School are not given equal opportunity for middle, secondary and higher education levels. Situation is vulnerable for Children with Disabilities (CWDs) particularly in low-income countries. CWDs should need equal access to quality

education because this is a fundamental key to form human capital and their participation in social and economic life. Besides that, Government should shown interest for vocational training of PCPs. Education is the most powerful instrument to develop socio-economic status of status of PCPs. Education for CWDs, is played an important role. From the educational system of India, a considerable segment of CWDs is excluded.

Due to educational policy of Government of India for disabled persons, education is satisfactory compared to other areas. The National Policy on Education for PCPs is responsible to integrate the physically and mentally impaired children with main stream educational institutions.

According to me, we should need to change our own mindset that disabled persons are not different from us. Actually, they are differently abled persons in our society. Some examples of special persons who has been famous in our world are Helen Adams Keller (American Author, Political activist, Lecturer), Albert Einstein (Theoretical Physicist), Stephen William Hawking (Scientist).

Future Scope

The present review displays that the major public health problem in India is Disability, their magnitude (prevalence) is estimated in 2011 Census. Possibly, it is hoped that again census will happen soon. In future, many study can be completed with about special persons. Following below study can be good about disabled persons in future.

The Census play a big role to disabled persons life. Again Census is needed to know the burden of disabled persons and to know the Educational Status of differently abled persons in India. Small study is also needed to know the magnitude of disabled persons and their educational status and educational development in many places of India. Different types of disability is observed in India, that is why, every types need separately studied. Study may be done on educational problems and current policies of disabled persons in India. Further research may be conducted on disabled persons by taking variables like attention, interest, intelligence, academic performance, cognition and motivation, parents and teachers attitude. A comparison can also be studied between disabled children who study in special school and those who study in other schools with normal children.

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